

Interactions between Choosing Emojis on Social Media and Its Contexts with Personality Impacts

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2021. 9. 30

Abstract

Facial emojis are increasingly used in digital communication as non-verbal signals (e.g., gestures, facial expressions, eye contact) are mostly unavailable. Emoji provide a way to express nonverbal conversational cues in digital communication. Previous research on emoji use hints that people with different personality traits might interpret emojis differently (e.g., Jones, Wurm, Norville, & Mullins, 2020). We aim to investigate the potential influence of individuals' personalities on their emoji use in different contexts through a mixed-methods approach. For the pilot experiment, we surveyed 126 participants (age range 15- to 25-years) from China to collect data on the affective valence of 40 facial emojis. Twelve facial emojis were selected and classified into three categories (positive, neutral, and negative) based on their perceived valence. Later in the experiment, 114 participants are asked to read 18 paragraphs of short digital conversations with two contexts: positive and non-positive. Their task is to imagine themselves as the designated character in each conversation and choose the emoji that they think is the best fit to respond. The results turn out that participants are significantly more likely to use positive emojis in a positive context and negative emojis in non-positive contexts, with participants, have more fluctuations in choosing emojis under non-positive contexts. On the personality side, only the extroversion aspect of personality has statistical significance: under positive contexts, less extravagant participants tend to use more positive emoji in positive context compared to more extravagant participants; however, there is no significant difference between less and more extravagant participants in non-pos contexts. Theoretically, this study may contribute to a deeper understanding of the link between personality and emoji usage in different contexts. Practically, the results can help reducing misunderstandings in digital communication and improving user experiences in different social communication applications.

Keywords: emoji, context, personality, behavior science, digital communication.

Literature Review

People can gain information through wordings, facial expressions, actions, and clothing, receiving multiple stimuli simultaneously when communicating face-to-face. These stimuli lead to a refined, comprehensive understanding of chats. However, when this simple process is converted into an online version, people will encounter problems. People lose multiple stimuli but solely visual information. This information is simply composed of printed text, along with delayed feedback issues, making it difficult to convey precise, intense emotions. In recent years, emojis, simple icons that are presented in colorful form, are becoming increasingly widely popular in online chat. Emojis can be categorized into facial ones, animal ones, abstract ones, and solid items, each representing meaning straightforwardly. By adding emojis in chat, people can convey emotions much more effectively: sending a “grinning face”, people share joys; sending a “weary face”, people share helplessness and light anger. (Riordan, M. A. 2017) The facial emojis, with internal emotional valence, assist people to set up emotional icons and convey mood while chatting. The truth is emojis even come out earlier than social media in 1982.

Emojis are indispensable and successful icons. Emojis’ design requires knowledge from multiple fields: behavior science, psychology, graphic design..... These crossing fields give emojis multiple natures and different significances, and hence many novel research questions appeared. (Kaye, L. K. et al, 2017) In the psychology field, these research questions can be approximately divided into two categories: perception-related and social-related. The former category involves research on how individual differences, including gender differences, generation difference, culture differences, impact emojis’ comprehension, and application. Miller. H.J. et al (2016) included discussions about various interpretations of emojis. Aliannejadi et al (2021) suggest that emoji-enriched interfaces can lead to significant improvement in terms of children researching and applying relevant resources. Chen, Z. et al (2018) investigated the significance gender difference in using emojis based on 401 million messages from large-scale Android users that speak 58 different languages.

Prior researches focus on personality and emoji usage’s interaction suggests reliable conclusions. Li et al (2018) first researched the correlation between personality dimensions and emoji usage patterns under public settings. They studied 71,823 Twitter users and 75 million tweets, concluding that preferences of certain critical emojis can reflect one’s personality, i.e. “Thumbs up” & “Winking Face” reflect high extraversion, while “Sun” & “Party Popper” reflect high conscientiousness. Furthermore, Völkel et al. (2019) researched personality dimensions and emoji selections under private communications. By recruiting 646 people and applying the Big Five Personality Scale, researchers concluded that neuroticism, agreeableness, and extraversion, three aspects of the Big Five Personality Scale, in sequenced order from

greatest to smallest affect people's choice of emoji usage. These conclusions are consistent with Marengo's findings. Massey, S. (2021) conducted study to apply emojis to measure children's attitudes to mathematics because emojis aid the experiment's reliability and validity as it is the most popular, direct, and influential icon in the digital era. Marengo et al (2017) composed a scale and employed 91 emojis as items to assess human personality; this is opposite from the personality scales people conventionally recognize, the ones with a bunch of personal questions and require participants to make choices. Marengo et al used a sample of 234 young adults, and they summarized that 36 of the 91 emoji significantly related to extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism, while zero of them related to openness or conscientiousness. This provides a novel perspective in designing personality scales while employing emojis has advantages of low facial validity and attractive nature. All these researches indicate emoji's potential interaction with other fields.

Apart from research focus on emojis at the item level, some scholars further connected emojis with their major function: facilitate understanding in online chatting. Thomas Holtgraves, Caleb Robinson (2020) employed 36 critical scenes followed by a question and some replies. Some of the replies contain emoji icons while others don't. 72 participants choose comments based on their understanding of these short conversations. The results revealed that Intended, indirect meanings are recognized more often, and more quickly when the reply contained an emoji. Emoji's function is preliminarily testified in their research. Based on the above researches, we have conducted the research, aiming to connect emojis, personality traits, and emoji's social function to study their interrelationship.

Research Questions

There are two basic research questions. The primary research question is how people choose emojis under different contexts while chatting on social media. People communicate under different contexts each day, and they have different emotions while chatting under them. (Riordan, M. A., 2017; Tian, Y. et al, 2017) Those contexts are about daily life's happiness, surprises, anger, regrets, sorrows. These can be divided into three essential categories: positive contexts (i.e. happiness, rewardful) neutral contexts (i.e. surprise, commenting, envy), and negative contexts (i.e. regrets, sorrow). By breaking them down in this way, we convert contexts to ordinal variables. In the pilot research, we analyzed several communication scenarios with different contexts, then we found out that while in positive and neutral scenes people might use emojis with different emotional valence, in negative contexts people all use emojis with negative valence. Since we consider people as consistent inability and it is easy for them to perceive and give reactions to contexts with negative emotions, we predict that in the experiment people would also behave similarly. Hence, we deleted "negative contexts" from

three context categories, and the primary research question becomes the relationship between choosing emojis to use and the two contexts (positive contexts and non-positive contexts).

The secondary research question is the relationship between how people choose emojis to use and the personality difference in five dimensions. As a social media's "byproduct", the behavior of choosing emojis can reflect one's emotion under the scenarios. (Wagner, A. et al, 2020) Considering choosing emojis may be impacted not only by one's emotion but also by his or her personality so that we can quantify the personality into "z score". The personality acts as covariates in this research.

Hence, the two basic research questions are:

RQ1. How people choosing emojis is affected by positive and non-positive contexts of the communication scenarios.

RQ2. How people choosing emojis is affected by people's personalities.

Hypotheses:

H1: People tend to use more positive rather than neutral emojis under positive contexts.

H2: People tend to use more neutral emojis rather than negative or positive emojis under non-positive contexts.

H3: People with a higher score in neuroticism tend to use more negative or neutral emojis in any context.

H4: People with a higher score in agreeableness tend to use more positive emojis in any context.

H5: People with a higher score in extraversion tend to use more positive emojis in any context.

Pilot Tests

Platform selection:

The aim of this research is not to investigate the difference of choosing emojis at different platforms, so we try to choose emojis consistently from a single platform. Even though most emojis are similar universally, there are slight differences among each of them on different platforms. The same emoji item might be slightly different in size, color, and shape arrangement at Twitter, Facebook, Google, Apple, and Samsung platforms. Chinese people use WeChat, QQ, and Weibo mostly in their daily lives, and emojis on those platforms even have more significant differences compared to previously mentioned platforms. The example item "Face of tears with joy" looks like

🥲 on apple, 😄 on google, 😂 on Microsoft, 😂 on Twitter.

In the pilot test, we surveyed how the mainstream social media Chinese people use and the frequency they use different platforms. Tian, Y. et al (2017) conducted research on 21,000 Facebook posts to study the interplay between emojis and the linguistic texts. Al Rashdi, F. (2018) researched on the emojis' functioning on Whatsapp. Since most Chinese people do not get access to platforms such as Twitter and Google, we finally selected most emojis from the Apple platform. We also selected some emojis from the dominant online chatting application, Wechat, as Wechat emojis have developed for eight years and there is significant interpretation change among them.

Emoji selection:

12 emojis were finally selected either from Emojipedia or from Wechat, and the emojis were selected after a pilot test. Based on previous emoji studies, we selected 40 representative emojis from Emojipedia, Wechat, and QQ. Then we did a pilot test questionnaire. This questionnaire requires participants to rate the emotional valence of each emoji. The questionnaire contained two essential parts. The first part collects information on participants' preference of chatting applications (Wechat or QQ). The second part includes 40 emojis with scales respectively. The scale is ranged from 0 to 10, which represents extremely negative emotional valence to extremely positive emotional valence. We excluded all emojis that require specific context to apply, i.e. face screaming in fear and all emojis with specific, implicit meaning, i.e. lemon face was excluded because it means jealousy in an implicit way. (Kaye, L. K. et al, 2017)

Of the 126 participants, the average age was 18.6 (min=13, max=25). 7.9% of participants aged range under 15, 73.0% ranged from 16 to 20, and 19.1% ranged from 21 to 25. Since 34.9% of participants prefer using QQ and 65.1% people prefer Wechat, we removed QQ emojis from the final selection. For emojis' emotional valence score range from 0 to 10, we define that if an emoji's average score is higher than 5.5, it is a positive emoji; If the average score ranges between 4.5 and 5.5, it is a neutral emoji; If the average score ranged is below 4.5, it is a negative emoji. We eventually selected four positive emojis, four neutral emojis, and four negative emojis. (Hu, T. et al, 2017)

We classified emojis with S.D. higher than 2.318 as controversial emojis. Three items (grin, facepalm, smile) were classified as controversial emojis, and we later conducted interviews on how these emojis' interpretations have changed over time and generation. By analyzing the rank of S.D. of the 40 emoji's emotional valence score from the highest to the lowest, we discover positive or neutral emojis take up 90% of the high S.D. score range, while most negative emojis and a small part of neutral emojis take up 80% of the low S.D. range. This indicates that positive emojis are much more likely to cause various interpretations, and their meaning can change significantly through generations.

Personality measure test:

We adopted the Big Five Personality Scale to measure people's personality traits. (Liu, S., & Sun, R., 2020) The Big Five Personality theory indicates that people's personality is basically from the major five dimensions: neuroticism, extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness. Neuroticism refers to whether a person is sensitive, nervous or resilient, and confident. Extroversion refers to whether he or she is outgoing, extrovert, or introvert. Agreeableness refers to whether one is compassionate or critical, rational. Conscientiousness refers to whether one is organized, efficient or careless. Openness refers to whether one is inventive, curious, or consistent and cautious.

We used a Chinese version of the Big Five Personality Scale modified by Wang Mengcheng et al (2011). This scale has 40 questions, with 8 questions to measure each of the personality dimensions. In the pilot test, 12 high school students (age 16-18) did this questionnaire. This is a reliable questionnaire ($\alpha=0.747$). Therefore, we adopt this questionnaire in later research.

Methodology & Procedure

Participants:

We recruited all 114 participants via the Weibo platform. All participants gave informed consent and were clearly debriefed at the end. Of the 114 participants, the average age is 18.5 (minimum age=12, maximum age=28), which is consistent with the pilot group. As we aim to research young people and try to exclude the generation difference, the participants of the pilot test, the questionnaire, and the interview are mostly teenagers. 81.2% of participants in the questionnaire are female, and 18.8% are male. We also collect information on social media use. 58.5% of participants prefer Wechat, and 41.5% of participants prefer QQ. All participants claim that they use Chinese social media platforms (i.e. Weibo, Douban). 32.0% of participants use them under one hour each day, 53.7% of participants use them between 1 and 3 hours each day, 9.5% of them use them between 3 and 5 hours, and 4.8% of them use them longer than 5 hours each day. Only 21.1% of people get access to foreign social media (i.e. Twitter, Facebook, Instagram), and 87.1% of them use those social media for under one hour each day. Hence, we confirm that use the most familiar Chinese social media emoji is advisable.

Experimental design & procedure (questionnaire)

When designing the structure that allows participants to choose emojis to fit into mock online communication with contexts change essentially, we referred to Thomas Holtgraves, Caleb Robinson (2020)'s experiment on use emojis to facilitate conveying indirect meaning in online communication. Thomas et al adopted 36 scenes that are followed by questions and replies. All

scenes include two people's online communication with a later question and reply exchange of mind. The 36 questions can be divided into 3 categories: either a request for an opinion, a request for disclosure, or a request for action. All replies show negative attitudes towards the above opinions, disclosure, or actions, such as expressing the opinions or disclosure is flawed. All replies were also divided into 3 categories, with one-third contain words and an emoji, one-third contain only words, and one-third only contain one emoji. Participants then need to judge whether the interpretation of replies is plausible. 24 of the scenarios were adopted from the earlier research, and 12 of the scenarios were newly written. Based on this experiment, we form a similar experimental design.

The whole questionnaire includes three parts: the critical part that measures the relationship of choosing emojis and context difference, the latter part that measures people's personality, and the final part that collects demographic information. We arrange the questionnaire in this sequence so that participants will not suspect the objective of the personality test, and they won't be fatigued when doing the most critical test on contexts and choosing emojis. Question 1 essentially asks for participants' consent.

For the first part (questions 2 to 19), we write 18 scenarios on two people's short online communication, each with 50 to 200 words. The communication is a short chat between two characters "me" and "my friend". The participants need to substitute themselves into "me" characters and reply to his or hers friend by choosing one emoji. We designed the interface of each question into Wechat form to simulate the scenarios. Both characters "me" and "my friend" have portraits like Wechat, and the text's size and typeface are also similar to Wechat. The 18 scenarios are divided into two categories: 9 are classified as positive context, the other 9 as non-positive contexts. We vague the boundary between neutral and negative because, in the pilot test, participants show consistency in choosing similar emojis under negative contexts. In 9 positive contexts, we wrote scenarios including emotions of explicit success, relief, contentment, appreciation, joy, expectation. In the 9 non-positive contexts, we wrote scenarios including emotions of jealousy, awkwardness, regret, anger, boredom. Each scenario corresponds to one emotion, without repetition. Under each of the 18 scenarios, there were 12 emojis. Participants need to choose one from those emojis to reply to his or her "friend". The sequence of these 18 scenarios is randomized among participants.

Question 20 to question 59 is the second part, which is the Big Five Personality Scale monitored by WangMengCheng et al (2013). This is a 40-question scale that requires participants to rate themselves in five dimensions of personality. In each question, there is a statement that measures one personality trait. Participants then need to choose the extent they agree that the statements precisely describe themselves. This is a 5-point scale, ranging from very disagree to very agree. The sequence of five dimensions measured is neuroticism, conscientiousness,

agreeableness, openness, extroversion.

The third part (questions 60 to 67) measures participants' demographic information. Apart from the basic information of age and gender, we ask participants their preferences and habits of using social media. Question 63 asks for participants' daily time spend on Wechat or QQ. Question 65 asks for participants' daily time use on domestic social media, and question 67 asks for their time use on foreign social media.

The questionnaire is spread through the Chinese online questionnaire platform "WenJuanXing", a platform that allows people to edit the questionnaire and send it out through the link. Participants can directly open it through the link, and there is a brief introduction of the study at the beginning. Participants are encouraged to open it on the phone to mock real-life communication scenarios. The average time of taking the questionnaire is 416.82 seconds.

Experimental design & procedure (interview)

We design interviews to research the three critical items. The three items are smile 😊, grin 😁, and facepalm 🤔. These are chosen because people have various interpretations of them (the items that have $S.D. > 2.318$), their implicit meaning is different from the apparent emotional valence, or their meaning has changed significantly after generations. The smile appears to be a positive icon, but it has a mean emoji score of 1.59, an extremely negative score. We, therefore, design interviews to take an insight into these three emojis. (Hu, T. et al, 2017)

We design a semi-structured interview. In the interview, we first briefly introduce the purpose of the study. We tell participants "This is a research on how people choose different emojis when communicating in daily life, and this we hold this interview to investigate three specific emoji items. The emojis I am referring to are the similes, usually round-icon emojis, but not include the "internet memes" that netizens create." If the participant does not understand what we mean, we will explain the definition of emojis until he or she completely understands. There are five participants, and all of them come from a senior high school in Beijing, as the age is consistent to the age of pilot tests and questionnaires. The whole process of the interview is recorded after getting participants' permits.

The whole interview can be divided into three parts, and it is conducted in a fixed sequence. The first part is the general questions. There are three general questions: Q1. Do you use emojis while chatting in daily life? Q2. How would you describe the frequency of using emojis? Q3. Why do you use emojis in daily life? These three questions aim to have an insight into people's habits of using emojis.

The second part is composed of 5 specific questions. Because there are three critical items, we ask each of the 5 questions three times, each time substitute one of the critical items as “this emoji”. We choose the critical item on Wechat and point it to the participants when asking questions on them instead of direct telling participants each of the emoji’s names to eliminate semantic input. These are the five questions: Q4. How do you think of “this emoji”? Q5. Under what circumstances will you use “this emoji”? Q6. How do you feel when receiving “this emoji”? Q7. What do you think the frequency that people use this emoji is? Is there a change in the frequency that people use it? Q8. Please recall the unforgettable case when you use “this emoji”; why do you choose this case? These five questions are asked three times in order to go through all three items.

The last part is optional. Whenever participants talk about the frequency change in the specific item, we ask them an additional question nine: do you think there is significant changes in meanings of emojis in recent years? Participants mostly give long answers on this question, and we dig deeper into reasons through tracking participants’ answers, but we don’t say words that participants do not say. After this part of the interview ends, we fully debrief the purpose and the whole process of the interview.

Results & Analyses

Emoji Selection

Table 1 shows the emoji score analysis for 40 emojis in the pilot test. The 40 emojis were rated for their emotional valence from 0 to 10, and we calculated the mean score and S.D. Emojis that have a score higher than 5.500 are noted as positive emojis; emojis with scores between 4.500 and 5.500 are noted as neutral emojis; emojis lower than 4.500 are noted as negative emojis. The 12 emojis that were selected are noted * in the category column. (Emojis downloaded from Wechat and QQ have slight skew in this table.)

Emoji	Unicode Name	Mean	S.D.	Category
	Face with tears of joy	7.483	2.164	Positive*
	Grinning face with smiling eyes	5.871	2.465	Positive
	Winking face	7.845	1.798	Positive
	Smiling face with heart-shaped eyes	7.362	2.272	Positive
	Face throwing a kiss	8.129	1.976	Positive
	Face with stuck-out tongue and tightly-closed eyes	6.750	2.076	Positive
	Smirking face	6.017	2.055	Positive

	Unamused face	3.586	1.805	Negative
	Flushed face	5.379	1.765	Neutral*
	Loudly crying face	4.897	2.547	Neutral*
	Face screaming in fear	4.362	2.222	Negative
	Face with cold sweat	2.948	2.004	Negative*
	Face with open mouth and cold sweat	3.224	2.047	Negative*
	Grimacing face	3.897	1.739	negative
	Pensive face	3.552	1.904	Negative
	Face with stuck-out tongue and winking eye	5.707	2.162	Positive
	Kissing face with closed eyes	7.293	2.030	Positive
	White smiling face	6.871	2.199	Positive
	Smiling face with	6.224	2.901	Positive*
	Relieved face	5.922	2.077	Positive*
	Doge	7.103	2.199	Positive
	Salute	7.371	2.111	Positive
	Grin	5.112	2.882	Neutral*
	Cute	5.026	2.970	Neutral
	Facepalm	6.888	2.318	Positive*
	Cold Sweat	4.948	2.071	Neutral
	Hurt	5.069	2.470	Neutral*
	Smile	1.586	1.957	Negative*
	Cannot help	4.879	2.186	Neutral
	Hey	6.922	2.089	positive
	Smart	6.828	2.035	Positive
	Jealousy	5.198	2.260	Neutral
	Awkward	3.526	1.972	Negative*
	Hard on the eyes	4.638	2.238	Neutral
	Broken	3.914	2.420	Negative
	Query	4.328	2.112	Negative
	Drool	5.974	2.815	Positive
	Cry	4.716	2.050	Neutral
	Sweat	3.466	1.963	negative
	Wow	6.853	2.433	Positive

Table 1

Questionnaire

We first analyze the main effect: the relationship between choosing emojis and the contexts' emotional valence. (Tian, Y. et al, 2017) We operationalize the “emoji” by calculating the

“emoji score”. We vague emoji items themselves but analyze them through categories on a holistic view. We calculate two scores: one for the score under positive context, the other under non-positive contexts. Of the 9 scenarios under one context, we calculate the score based on the emotional valence of the emojis that the participants choose. A positive corresponds to +1 point, neutral correspond to 0 points, and negative corresponds to -1 point. We eventually add up the total score for each context, so one’s final emoji score ranges from -9 to +9 points. For example, participant A chooses 5 positive emojis, 2 neutral emojis, and 2 negative emojis under positive context, then his final emoji score for positive context is $5 \times (+1) + 2 \times 0 + 2 \times (-1) = +3$. In this way, we convert the nominal variable (emojis participant chose) to the scale variable.

We apply generalized estimating equation (GEE) to analyze both contexts’ effect and the personality’s effect. For all 114 non-positive contexts, the mean emoji score $\mu = 0.432$, the upper bound= 0.772, the lower bound= 0.093. For 114 positive contexts, the mean emoji score $\mu = 4.928$, the upper bound= 5.267, the lower bound= 4.588. Table 2 reports that emojis participants choose significantly relate to the context that the communication happens. Participants prefer using positive emojis in positive contexts than in non-positive contexts. Hence, it can be concluded that contexts play a significant role in affecting one’s emoji scores (*Wald $X^2(1)=351.02, p < .001$*). The lower bound of the 95% Wald Confidence Interval is 4.037, and the upper bound is 4.980. The standard error is .241. This is consistent with hypothesis 1 and hypothesis 2. Participants tend to use more positive emojis when under positive contexts, and they use more neutral emojis under non-positive contexts, arguably because people can have various interpretations towards non-positive emojis, and these emojis can fit in more contexts.

After analyzing all five dimensions of personality, we conclude that only extroversion of the five personality dimensions significantly relates to people choosing emojis (*Wald $X^2(2)=7.09, p=.008$*). The lower bound of the 95% Wald Confidence Interval is -1.091; the upper bound is -.166. The standard error is .236. To further analyze extroversion’s effect, we categorize people with extroversion score > 23 as more extrovert people, people with extroversion score < 23 as less extrovert people. Table 2 hence shows that less extroverted people are more likely to choose positive emojis when contexts change from non-positive to positive compared to more extroverted people. This is different from the hypothesis, probably because though less outgoing when getting along with people in daily life, less extrovert people prefer to socialize and show their opinions while chatting online. The interactions between extroversion and how people choose emojis are shown in graph 1.

Parameter Estimates (95% Wald Confidence Interval)

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Lower	Upper	Wald Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Intercept	.439	.213	.021	.856	4.247	1	.039
Pos=1, non-pos=0=1	4.509	.241	4.037	4.980	351.023	1	.000
Zscore (Neuro)	-.146	.214	-.564	.272	.468	1	.494
Zscore (Agree)	-.163	.240	-.633	.307	.462	1	.497
Zscore (Extro)	.318	.214	-.102	.738	2.209	1	.137
Pos=1, non-pos=0=1*Zscore (Neuro)	-.110	.229	-.558	.338	.232	1	.630
Pos=1, non-pos=0=1*Zscore (Agree)	-.166	.240	-.636	.305	.475	1	.490
Pos=1, non-pos=0=1*Zscore (Extro)	-.628	.236	-1.091	-.166	7.088	1	.008
(Scale)	4.208						

Dependent variable: emoji.outcome

Table 2

Graph 1

Interview

We interview 5 participants on their view of the three critical items. (smile 😊, grin 😁, and facepalm 🤔) Generally, all participants use emojis in their daily life. People all use emojis in high frequency, and most people claim that they would use emojis in a higher frequency when chatting with acquaintances. Sometimes the frequency and the specific emoji one chooses to

depend on the chatter's identity. Participants claim that they prefer to choose simple, smiling emojis while chatting with people of higher social status because those emojis can reduce embarrassment and show friendliness. The reasons that people use emojis are similar: people agree that emojis can help to better express their ideas, and they can show implicit meanings that text cannot show. For example, "smile 😏" strongly shows speechlessness and anger. All participants agree that people's frequency of using these emojis decreased these years, and their meanings changed significantly, some even changed several times.

Specifically, for item "smile 😏", all people agree that "smile" is a negative emoji, and some demonstrate that this emoji has multiple meanings: 1. Show satire, especially when chatting with those friends; 2. Show that he is annoyed by the other people involved in the chat; 3. Show a speechless mood. Weissman, B., & Tanner, D. (2018) researched on how the brain processes sarcastic emojis when it interpreting them. However, when asking their feelings when receiving a "smile", most participants agree that this depends on different scenarios. When receiving "smiles" from elder people, people feel normal and acceptable because they think elder people do not understand how the younger generation views different emojis. When receiving a "smile" from contemporary people, they would suspect they annoyed others. When asking about people's using frequency of "smile", most participants agree that people use it less in recent days. Some think that "smile" looks horrible, and some think it is because people prefer to customize emojis (memes). Most participants mention unpleasant, awkward experiences of using the "smile" emoji.

For the second item "grin 😁", participants demonstrate that it also has different meanings. 1. Show genuine joy and happiness; 2. Mock at something; 3. Show anger at something, and the extent is higher than "smile". People agree that people use less "grin" on Wechat, but much more on Weibo, one of the mainstream social media in China. "Grin" explicitly shows sarcasm in most people's mind, but still, some people think this simply show joy. People's interpretations of "grin" vary a lot, and their opinions are polarized. Some people take examples of happiness and expectations when they are asked to give a scenario of using "grin", and some list teasings with their friends.

For the third item "facepalm 🤦", participants all hold that this expresses reluctance and couldn't help, politeness when asking for help, implicit showing refuse and sorrow, and defusing embarrassment. People express that they often use "facepalm", especially chatting with someone that they are not familiar with or talking about work issues. However, people all agree that people use less "facepalm" when chatting with friends nowadays because it is a

symbol for unfamiliar. Some people suggest that people use most “facepalm” in 2016. People all give examples of using “facepalm” when expressing apologies.

Conclusion & Discussion:

This study aims to investigate the relationship between choosing emojis and different contexts of chatting, with 5 dimensions of personality traits as covariates. We used several questionnaires and interviews to research people’s habits of choosing and using emojis. The online questionnaires mock scenarios in people’s daily life when chatting, and it offers us reliable quantitative data. The interview specifically digs into people’s minds on reasons they prefer specific emojis.

Prior research on choosing emojis and contexts is limited. Most research is about suggestions on designing emojis for business purposes, various interpretations of emojis and methods to reduce them, and emojis overlapping different platforms. There are also emojis interactions with personality. Prior researchers often use emojis to predict people’s personality, some research concludes that specific emojis correspond to specific personality traits. Liu, S., & Sun, R. (2020) researched on how specific emojis help people with different personality traits to convey information and achieve different purposes in daily communication. However, the present research sets settings as the major independent variable, and we test the effects of choosing emojis under different contexts. We conclude that people use positive emojis under positive contexts, but use neutral emojis, especially those with various interpretations, under non-positive contexts. Emojis with high standard deviation reflect people’s various interpretations of them. The difference in those interpretations and using habits are mostly affected by one’s generation and the time they interact with social media. People in the same generation often have similar interpretations. (Alshenqeeti, H., 2016). However, the new generation now tends to interpret each emoji in a negative way as they believe many people show mystifying and voice dripping with sarcasm. Specifically, in China, emojis that are apparently positive are more likely to be interpreted in various ways since many people argue that the apparent positive icons are actually negative, i.e. smiles are like masks, and they show apparent happiness but genuinely satire. (Weissman, B., & Tanner, D., 2018)

Non-positive contexts include so many scenarios with different emotions, and we devise these scenarios to research how people can best express themselves through texts and one emoji. We want participants to choose the most representative emoji to convey their emotions. Emojis indeed help to convey emotions, especially help to convey those with neutral valence but have strong connections with others. (Willoughby, J. F., & Liu, S., 2018; Pfeifer, V. A. et al, 2021) People cannot easily express emotions, i.e. envies and speechlessness, through online chatting because they cannot see each other’s facial expressions and texts are too thin.

The relationship between choosing emojis and personality traits is not as strong as we hypothesized. Only extroversion trait has a relationship with choosing emojis. Less extraverted people are more likely to choose positive emojis when contexts change from non-positive to positive compared to more extraverted people. There are two potential explanations. The first explanation is that online chatting inevitably provides space for each other, so less extroverted people use more positive emojis to reduce the distance between themselves and the chatters. On the other hand, more extroverted people may presume that friends in online chatting are close enough that they can communicate well through texts, and they do not need to show extra passion through using positive, vivid emojis. The second explanation is that less extroverted people are fear being enthusiastic when actually interacting with people, but they can express themselves passionately during online chatting, so they use more open emojis. Further studies are needed to give accurate explanations for the relationship between extroversion and how people choose emojis.

Overall, we conclude that people choose various emojis for non-positive contexts because they all have their own interpretations and using habits. When chatters' interpretations of one emoji are opposite, the chat will become awkward. Therefore, it is better to add simple texts to icons to prevent misinterpretations. (Willoughby, J. F., & Liu, S. 2018) For example, many emojis look smiling on the face hold a sign of "OK". People now prefer these kinds of emojis as they are more vivid and create fewer misunderstandings. Furthermore, people also prefer to use photoshop to create their own "memes". "Memes" are becoming increasingly popular that many people prefer these to traditional emojis, probably because these combinations of pictures and texts can effectively help people to express themselves. (Pfeifer, V. A. et al, 2021)

The study generally has some strengths. First, we form a reliable questionnaire to test the main effect, and the questionnaire can be finished in 10 minutes, so most people do not fill out answers without considerations. Second, the interview helps us to research the deep reasons on how the emoji interpretation changes over time and the potential reasons. The interview is helpful and it provided us much valid qualitative data.

Limitations & Future Expectations:

Our study has several weaknesses. First, the mock chatting scenarios cannot perfectly fit in people's actual online chatting process. People do not see a picture of chatting history and then reply, but receive messages in real-time. Therefore, the ecological validity is reduced. Second, the Big Five Personality Scale directly asks participants for personality traits, and hence it has high face validity. It is also a simplification version, so the overall validity is reduced. People in China often complain that they cannot accurately measure themselves in the conditions provided by the questionnaires. Therefore, the scale may not accurately reflect people's personalities. Third, the age group of this study is highly limited to 15 to 25. However, age and

generation differences play important roles in affecting how one interprets and uses emojis. The age group is limited, so the overall generality is low. Though prior studies suggest that elder people use much more positive emojis, future studies are expected to combine the elder people in the research to study how they interpret positive emojis and how different contexts affect their use of emojis. (Herring, S. C., & Dainas, A. R., 2020) Research on the interrelationship between age group, personality, and how people use emojis are also expected.

References:

- Aliannejadi, M., Landoni, M., Huibers, T., Murgia, E., & Pera, M. S. (2021, March). Children's Perspective on How Emojis Help Them to Recognise Relevant Results: Do Actions Speak Louder Than Words?. In *Proceedings of the 2021 Conference on Human Information Interaction and Retrieval* (pp. 301-305).
- Al Rashdi, F. (2018). Functions of emojis in WhatsApp interaction among Omanis. *Discourse, context & media*, 26, 117-126.
- Alshenqeeti, H. (2016). Are emojis creating a new or old visual language for new generations? A socio-semiotic study. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 7(6).
- Chen, Z., Lu, X., Ai, W., Li, H., Mei, Q., & Liu, X. (2018, April). Through a gender lens: learning usage patterns of emojis from large-scale Android users. In *Proceedings of the 2018 World Wide Web Conference* (pp. 763-772).
- Herring, S. C., & Dainas, A. R. (2020). Gender and age influences on interpretation of emoji functions. *ACM Transactions on Social Computing*, 3(2), 1-26.
- Holtgraves, T., & Robinson, C. (2020). Emoji can facilitate recognition of conveyed indirect meaning. *PloS one*, 15(4), e0232361.
- Hu, T., Guo, H., Sun, H., Nguyen, T. V., & Luo, J. (2017, May). Spice up your chat: the intentions and sentiment effects of using emojis. In *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media* (Vol. 11, No. 1).
- Kaye, L. K., Malone, S. A., & Wall, H. J. (2017). Emojis: Insights, affordances, and possibilities for psychological science. *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 21(2), 66-68.
- Liu, S., & Sun, R. (2020). To express or to end? Personality traits are associated with the reasons and patterns for using emojis and stickers. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 1076.
- Li, W., Chen, Y., Hu, T., & Luo, J. (2018, June). Mining the relationship between emoji usage patterns and personality. In *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media* (Vol. 12, No. 1).
- Marengo, D., Giannotta, F., & Settanni, M. (2017). Assessing personality using emoji: An exploratory study. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 112, 74-78.
- Massey, S. (2021). Using Emojis and drawings in surveys to measure children's attitudes to mathematics. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 1-13.
- Miller, H. J., Thebault-Spieker, J., Chang, S., Johnson, I., Terveen, L., & Hecht, B. (2016, March). "Blissfully Happy" or "Ready to Fight": Varying Interpretations of Emoji. In *Tenth international AAAI conference on Web and social media*.
- Pfeifer, V. A., Armstrong, E. L., & Lai, V. T. (2021). Do all facial emojis communicate emotion? The impact of facial emojis on perceived sender emotion and text processing. *Computers in Human Behavior*,

107016.

Riordan, M. A. (2017). Emojis as tools for emotion work: Communicating affect in text messages. *Journal of Language and Social Psychology, 36*(5), 549-567.

Tian, Y., Galery, T., Dulcinati, G., Molimpakis, E., & Sun, C. (2017, April). Facebook sentiment: Reactions and emojis. In *Proceedings of the Fifth International Workshop on Natural Language Processing for Social Media* (pp. 11-16).

Völkel, S. T., Buschek, D., Pranjic, J., & Hussmann, H. (2019, October). Understanding emoji interpretation through user personality and message context. In *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction with Mobile Devices and Services* (pp. 1-12).

Wagner, A., Marusek, S., & Yu, W. (2020). Emojis and Law: contextualized flexibility of meaning in cyber communication. *Social Semiotics, 30*(3), 396-414.

Weissman, B., & Tanner, D. (2018). A strong wink between verbal and emoji-based irony: How the brain processes ironic emojis during language comprehension. *PloS one, 13*(8), e0201727.

Willoughby, J. F., & Liu, S. (2018). Do pictures help tell the story? An experimental test of narrative and emojis in a health text message intervention. *Computers in Human Behavior, 79*, 75-82.

Zhang, X., Wang, M. C., He, L., Jie, L., & Deng, J. (2019). The development and psychometric evaluation of the Chinese Big Five Personality Inventory-15. *PloS one, 14*(8), e0221621.